

THE DIFFERENCE AND SIMILARITIES BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK FOLKLORE

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Abstract. *The term folklore is the most essential genre in literature because of its role in shaping the culture, tradition and history of humanity for many centuries. The interaction of folklore with other literary genres is inseparable and complete each other with many ways. However, there some little changes among the folk genres of several nations. The main aim of this research paper is to analyze the strike differences between English and Uzbek folklore and will give examples to prove the views of the research.*

Keywords: *folklore, folk tales and epics, artistic thinking, poetics, lyrics, drama, idea, tradition.*

РАЗНИЦА И СХОДСТВО АНГЛИЙСКОГО И УЗБЕКСКОГО ФОЛЬКЛОРА

Аннотация. *Термин фольклор является наиболее важным жанром в литературе из-за его роли в формировании культуры, традиций и истории человечества на протяжении многих веков. Взаимодействие фольклора с другими литературными жанрами неразрывно и во многом дополняет друг друга. Однако есть небольшие изменения среди фольклорных жанров ряда народов. Основная цель данной исследовательской работы состоит в том, чтобы проанализировать существенные различия между английским и узбекским фольклором и привести примеры, подтверждающие точку зрения исследования.*

Ключевые слова: *фольклор, народные сказки и былины, художественное мышление, поэтика, лирика, драматургия, идея, традиция.*

I. Introduction

In nearly all genres of folklore, the description of main heroes is always idealized with many ways, including his behavior, character, personality and actions in life. The hero is recognizable with his masses in life to everyone in his country which can be one factor for catch the attention of readers. This way of describing is not only quite famous in English folklore but also in every nation's piece of writing.

From prehistoric times, surviving was not the only reason of fighting, but longevity had a main role. As a result, some folk genres such as the content of alla, rubbish, fairy tales and riddles, had been aimed at shaping a conscious, strong, agile and agile human upbringing. People's perceptions of the world around them and the accumulated knowledge about it, wise sayings and conclusions based on life experience, are conveyed to children in the form of specific advices in a way that is understandable to them. That is why there is a lot in common in the folklore of different peoples, even in countries very far from each other.

II. Methods

During a research the books about fairy tales and folk ballads are read carefully to identify the strike changes. The similarity and commonality of Uzbek and English folklore can be seen the same in prehistoric times due to the fact that the development of humanity is the same and expected nearly identical in all phases of life in terms of literary genres as well. The first to record, examine and publish some samples of Uzbek folklore were European

tourists, ambassadors and scientists who lived in the second half of the XIX century and the beginning of the XX century. From that time people made themselves happy and find hope to overcome their problems or living despite the hardships they face. They sang several songs and stay happy with it. Main heroes of folk ballads and tails were their edifying people from whom they can learn and believe in.

III. Results

While researching the difference between English and Uzbek folklore some noticeable similarities are identified as well. Let's take Beowulf and Alpomish as an example. Both of these characters are so brave and courageous and dedicated themselves for their nation and motherland to protect it from enemies. The given description of these two characters is similar. Even the sequence of events happened nearly the same order.

When it comes to the fairy tales, it is common that most of them end with the victory of a virtue from darkness. Every child knows at least one fairy tale and can retell it, which shows and proves that the teaching children to goodness is always the main priority in every nation despite their language, culture and religion. Hence, depicting the moral and plot of such tales is another similarity that could not be denied. To prove this idea some fairy tales like "Cinderella" and "Zumrad and Qimmat", "Beauty and The Beast" can be mentioned with a happy ending and the same human feelings like love, kindness, respect and love to the motherland.

Fairy tales show us the national wisdom and beauty of our mother tongue. While reading a lot of Uzbek and English fairy tales, it is noticeable that they have some similarities. We wonder what they have in common and how they differ. If we make a comparative study of Uzbek and English fairy tales, we can prove that fairy tales have similarities, while at the same time they have certain differences due to cultural and historical features of the people's development. Fairy tales are stories created by oral traditions. Their plots demonstrate strong conflicts between good and evil, with magic and luck and usually have happy endings. One can find universal human feelings such as love, hate, courage, kindness, and cruelty in typical fairy tales. Children should read and learn to understand fairy tales so that they can better realize the national literature as well as the culture of the country in whole. Folk tales reflect people's life, their history, beliefs, mentality. Different stages of nation's development are presented in them in a certain way.

IV. Conclusions

In short, folklore works as a creative product of the people have made a unique contribution to the development of world literature. In the history of nations and peoples, the issues of oral art occupy a leading place [3]. The main commonalities between the genres of folklore, the relations of principles, the similarity if folklore identify the self-enrichment of folklore. The general conclusion is that in English and Uzbek folk tales, the characters perform one function: they represent the mentality of their people and express it in a language that allows us to talk about the formation of the certain stereotype. Comparing the plots of English and Uzbek fairy tales, it must be said that the main difference between them lies in the fact that the Uzbek folk tale is based on a fiction, an unexpected turn of events, magic and transformation. In the centre of the English fairy tales is specific information about some facts of everyday life.

The fact that they are quite essential to the development of every nation is related to the meaning of their plot which depicts the feelings and opinions of a nation clearly.

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